

Review Article

G-D's Physics Revises the Universe's Cosmological & Astronomical "Time-Scaling"!

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Note: Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists (worldwide) to carry out a further direct empirical validation of the (already validated) New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm based on a "time-sensitive" measurement of a predicted increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – specifically during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH, New Year) two days' time-interval due at: September 16th -17th 2023 (and onwards), relative to before the 16th-17th of September! Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in this further direct validation of the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics. Dr. Bentovish's e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com.

Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a profound "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) & Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "A-Causal Computation" "G-D's Physics" (previously termed: "Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT)! This article presents empirical evidence supporting at least two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of this New "G-D's Physics" as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, thereby "crowning" "G-D's Physics" as the new satisfactory 21st century's Physics Paradigm! Indeed, the profound theoretical shift brought about by "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" stems from its discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ " (e.g., including their four basic physical features: "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" values). Based upon the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive Universal Frame/s, UF's) the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing either in the "same"- or "different"- UF's), thereby negating some of the basic assumptions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm including GRT's "Big-Bang" Model and "Darwin's Natural Selection Principle" Evolutionary Theory! Based upon the unequivocal validation of "G-D's Physics" unique "Universe's Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) "Critical Prediction", which supports "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) postulate leading to an UNCIARE at the Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH), a novel "Universe's Seven Days Origination" (USDO) alternative "G-D's Physics" Model of the universe's Cosmological & Astronomical Time-Scaling is proposed.

Introduction

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics has undergone a major "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) [1-47]. This "Paradigmatic-Shift" inevitably followed the appearance of a fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm signified by a basic "theoretical-inconsistency" between its (above-mentioned) constituting Models (e.g., GRT & QM), as well as its principle inability to explain the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion, e.g., assumed to be "caused" by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts, but could not be detected experimentally (despite over twenty years of intensive experimental efforts to do so)! Instead, the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) has been shown capable of resolving this (apparent) "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM based on its discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) UCP which simultaneously computes the four basic physical features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – in the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ " (!) thereby producing an extremely rapid series of UF's frames comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"!

According to Thomas Kuhn's [50], well-accepted analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions" [50], in order for science to accept such a "Paradigmatic-Shift" (in any given scientific sub-discipline), it is necessary for a few specific conditions to be fulfilled:

- a) The appearance of such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" (in that given discipline) signified by the existence of a "theoretical-inconsistency" between the "pillars" of the Old ("Material-Causal") Paradigm (e.g., GRT & QM, i.e., as mentioned above), as well as this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's principle inability to explain the accelerated expansion of the physical universe – e.g., assumed to "caused" by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the matter in the universe but which could not be detected experimentally despite numerous attempts to do so (despite twenty years of intensive experimentation)?!
- b) The ability of the New ("G-D's Physics") Scientific paradigm to resolve this apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM, as well as offer an alternative (satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the accelerated expansion of the universe: Based on "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's discovery of the singular

higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle's" (UCP's) simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), it has been shown that this UCP simultaneously computes all "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST) "particle/objects"; "Multiple Spatial-Temporal" (MST) "wave-phenomena"; and "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" "Universal Frame/s" computations! In this manner, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT's strict "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB) as opposed to QM's "Quantum Entanglement" phenomena's implication wherein a certain measurement of one subatomic "entangled particle's" ("complimentary pairs" value may "instantaneously" affect the other "entangled particle's" complimentary (energy/mass or time/mass) value?! This is simply because according to "G-D's Physics broader EST computation – which embeds (within it) the relatively more "constrictive" UCP's MST and SST computations, the apparent "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon merely represents the UCP's computation of "equivalent SST particle points" along the MST's (subatomic) "wave" computation, which is embedded within the broader EST UCP's computation! Alongside "G-D's Physics" new (profound) theoretical understanding, wherein the UCP's computation of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" is based on the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" i.e., "Framework" and "Consistency" four possible combinations: "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), and "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") possible combinations! Hence, "G-D's Physics" new theoretical framework has been shown capable of resolving this apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT's strict SLB's principle constraint imposed upon the transmission of any signal (or even information) across space and time – which seems to be contradicted by Quantum Entanglement's "instantaneous" effect of the measurement of one entangled particle's complimentary pairs' measurement upon the other entangled particle's complimentary value; based on the deeper theoretical understanding of "G-D's Physics" (novel) conceptualization and understanding wherein it is the simultaneous UCP's computation of "equivalent MST wave" "particle-points", coupled with its two "Computational Dimensions" complimentary exhaustive UCP's computation of "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time"), which can account for the apparent "entanglement" of two such "equivalent SST particle points" along the "MST wave" (simultaneous) computation of the UCP's "complimentary-exhaustive" "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") "complimentary pairs"!

Likewise, the New "G-D's Physics" theoretical framework offer a new (satisfactory) alternative theoretical explanation for the universe's empirically observed accelerated expansion! This new theoretical explanation of "G-D's Physics" is based on its (novel) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH) which stipulated that whenever there is a large group of individual human-beings all collectively focusing on this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), then this brings about an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE), e.g., such as during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" (New Year) two days' special time interval (in which Millions of Jews all over the world collectively focus on this singular UCP) – which was predicted to bring about such an "UNCIARE" increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!

c) Identification of at least one unique "Critical Prediction" which can differentiate the prediction of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM: according to Kuhn's⁵⁰ analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions", in order for any scientific discipline to accept a basic "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old ("Material-Causal") Paradigm to the New ("G-D's Physics") Paradigm it is necessary to identify at least one unique "Critical Prediction" that can differentiate the predictions of the

New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm from the Old "Material-Causal" GRT's and QM's predictions! Indeed, if at least one such (unique) "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm is verified as "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of the Old Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions – then (according to Kuhn's [50], well accepted analysis) that particular scientific discipline (e.g., in our case Theoretical Physics) has to accept the New "G-D's Physics" as the New (satisfactory) Physics Paradigm (for the Twenty-First Century)! Indeed, we've been blessed with such an identification of two such (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – which are being shown to be "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, therefore leading to the unequivocal acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Methods & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i..n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i..n) \leq n * h [\{UF's(i..n)\}]$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by Pohl et al. (2010):

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction Pohl et al.[54-56], set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i..n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force"⁴⁹, interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction^{53,57}, higher dimension gravity⁴⁸, a new boson⁵², and the quasi-free hypothesis

π^{+51} ; and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!.

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion [58-61]?! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG" Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated

Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Discussion

Based upon the above results indicating that there exist two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" that have been empirically validated – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, we must accept "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) as the New satisfactory Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics! As noted previously, this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm accomplishes several (very important) undertakings:

a) "G-D's Physics" resolves the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" that seems to exist between GRT & QM, e.g., based upon the discovery of the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (and its four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec⁻¹"), including "Single Spatial Temporal" (SST), Multi Spatial-Temporal (MST) and Exhaustive Spatial Temporal (EST) "UCP's differential computations.

b) "G-D's Physics" unifies (for the first time in Theoretical Physics) between those Four Physical Features, as well as between the Four Forces of Nature based on its novel discovered "Universal Computational Formula", which was also shown to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM (as indicated above) and in fact incorporate key elements from both GRT & QM within this singular UCF!

"G-D's Physics" Negation of Old "Material-Causal" Assumption!

However, since "G-D's Physics" represents an "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, e.g., stemming from its discovery regarding the simultaneity of the UCP's of all exhaustive spatial pixels' (four basic physical features) for each consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising each consecutive UF's frame/s) back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two UF's frames; therefore, this New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm negated the possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s! Hence, this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm was shown to challenge and in fact negate many of the basic assumptions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM, as well as Darwin's Natural Selection Principle, DNS evolutionary theory)!

The universe could not have been "created" or "caused" by the initially "Big-Bang" nuclear event – which is assumed to have "created" all of the suns, galaxies, mass and energy in the universe! This is because there could

not have existed any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – including between such as an assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event and it's "causing" the creation of any suns, galaxies, planets, mass or energy in the "first", "second" or "trillionth" etc. UF's frame/s! Nor could there exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) such exhaustive spatial pixels (or suns, galaxies, mass and energy) existing in any two consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby negating GRT's "Big-Bang" Model's assumption wherein the continuous expansion of the universe (at an accelerated rate till this very day!) is the result of this initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event?! Likewise, "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm also negates the possibility that the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts (assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe but which could not be verified experimentally despite over two decades of intensive scientific experimentation?!) could "cause" the accelerated expansion of the physical universe!? This is because (once more) there could exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" (concepts) and any "galactic-elements" at the "edges of the universe" which would "cause" these galactic elements to be "expulsed" (at an accelerated rate relative to the less distant galaxies, relative to Earth); as we've seen this stems from the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe for every consecutive UF's frame/s and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

More generally, "G-D's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) has indicated that this basic fundamental "material-causal" assumption of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm – underlying GRT's Einstein's Equations (e.g., including the "Big-Bang" event, "Cosmological Constant", and "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts) is principally negated, e.g., as leading to both "logical inconsistency" and "computational indeterminacy"?!

The "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP)

In much the same manner, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm was shown to negate "Darwin's Natural Selection Principle" (DNP), due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s! Hence, DNS's basic "material-causal" assumption, which assumes that there exists a direct (or even indirect) physical interaction/s between any given organism's genetic information and certain "Cosmic Rays" that "cause" certain "genetic-mutations" (in these organism) is strictly negated by the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" all of these exhaustive spatial pixels "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s). Likewise, "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" (e.g., simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s) negates DNP's other "material-causal" assumption, wherein it is assumed that it is the direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between this "genetically mutated" organism and certain "harsh environmental conditions" that allow this organism to "survive" these "harsh environmental conditions" (i.e., as opposed to all the other "un-mutated" organisms which are not able to survive these "harsh environmental conditions"), thereby passing this "genetically mutated organism's" genetic information to next generations – hence assumed to explain the evolution of the various Biological Species?! "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm was shown to strictly negate also this (second) "material-causal" assumption of DNP (once again) because due to the simultaneous computation of the UCP of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive

UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s) there cannot exist any such "material-causal" (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s!

The "Universal Computational Formula" Integration of the Four Physical Features!

Another very significant accomplishment of "G-D's Physics" New (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm is its proven capacity to completely integrate between the Four basic Physical Features, e.g., of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", based on its discovery of the singular "Universal Computational Formula"! As known, Einstein's GRT was only capable of unifying between certain "pairs" of these Four Physical Features, e.g., "space-time", and the "energy-mass equivalence", as well as the curvature of "Space-time" by massive objects etc. – but wasn't able to completely integrate these Four Physical Features together. In contrast, "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm was shown capable of completely unifying these Four Physical Features based on the discovery of the singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes all of these four Physical Features through its singular "Universal Computational Formula":

THE "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m} \quad \text{UF's } \{n...n...x\} [Px]_{\{a...z\}}$$

Note: which is accompanied by "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) computational (previous) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" as representing "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computational properties of the UCP's simultaneous and integrated computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels:

S: (f_i{x,y,z}{UF(i)} + ... f_j{x,y,z}{UF(n)}) / h * n {UF's} such that:

$$f_j\{x,y,z\}\{UF(n) \leq f_i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

$$E: (f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i...n)]$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i...n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] \neq O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i...n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

such that:

$$T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i...n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Significantly, it has been previously shown that this novel UCF possesses two equivalent "Relativistic Format" and "Quantum Format" which indicate that it embeds (within it) "special-cases" of well-known physical laws and characteristics of GRT such as the "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ("E = Mc²") and QM's "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" "complimentary pairs"; thereby pointing at "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's complete unification- embedding- and indeed transcending- of GRT & QM!

Indeed, coupled with the UCP's new computational definitions for its computation of each of these Four Physical Features as secondary computational features stemming from the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions", e.g., "Framework" (frame vs. object) and "Consistency" (consistent vs. inconsistent) four possible combinations (as described

previously), this newly discovered UCF completely unifies between these Four basic Physical Features, as well as between the Four Forces (as published previously).

The "Computational Invariance Principle" & "Universal Consciousness Reality" Theoretical Postulates

Another profound change made by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm is related to its discovery of the "Computational Invariance Principle" & associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" – as they completely alter our basic understanding of the physical universe from a "solid" independent material reality towards a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR)! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" "Computational Invariance Principle" theoretical postulate since only this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) exists "uniformly", "continuously" and "constantly" – both "during" its consecutive computation of every (subsequent) UF's frame (e.g., as simultaneously computing all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features of every consecutive UF's frame/s) and also solely exists "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe); whereas the entire physical universe (e.g., and of all its exhaustive spatial pixels) exists only "transiently" and "phenomenally" – "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely being computed by this singular UCP for each of its exhaustive spatial pixels), but "ceases to exist" and "dissolves" back into the singular UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames; therefore the "Computational Invariance Principle" infers that only the "computationally invariant" UCP exists "constantly", "uniformly" and "consistently" and is regarded as "computationally-invariant", as opposed to the only "computationally-variant" standing of the entire physical universe – which exists only "transiently" and "phenomenally" "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely produced by this singular "computationally-invariant" UCP, but ceases to exist and "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP)! This profound new realization of "G-D's Physics" "Computational Invariance Principle" also led to an associated (even more profound) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) theoretical postulate that reasoned that since only the "computationally-invariant" UCP exists "constantly", "consistently" and "uniformly", whereas the "computationally-variant" physical universe (e.g., and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") – as solely being computed by this singular "computationally-invariant" UCP; therefore according to the "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulate there only (truly) exists this singular "Universal Computational Principle" – which manifests "transiently" and "phenomenally" as the physical universe (and all of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, and remains solely (without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s)! In other words, according to these two (novel) "G-D's Physics" "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" there truly exists only one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists "constantly", "consistently" and "uniformly" – both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s exhaustive spatial pixels' (four basic physical features), and also (solely) exists "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s, with the physical universe being seen only as a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered UCR!

A "Pre-Planned Geulah Directed" Universe!

However, such a profound (totally) new understanding of the true nature of the entire physical universe – as representing only a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of this singular UCR (which alone can be considered as the "constant", "consistent" and "uniform" singular true reality underlying and indeed transcending the physical universe) questions and

challenges (and even negates) some of the basic (and most fundamental) assumptions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm! This is because we realize that not only the universe could not have been created (or "caused") by the (previously) assumed initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event (as explained above and previously due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all of those exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames!) Likewise, the continues (accelerated) expansion of the universe could not be explained by the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts or by the "Cosmological Constant", or in fact based on any of those three "Exceptional Expulsive Elements" (EEE's) associated with Einstein's Equations of General Relativity Theory (GRT), based on "G-D's Physics" CDP's detailed analysis and negation of the basic "Self-Referential Computational Structure" (SRCS) characterizing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's fundamental Computational Systems' structure!

But, if in fact, there truly exists only one singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP), and there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s, then we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the whole origination- ("dissolution"-) "sustenance"- and "development" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as its entirety!) is solely dependent upon the (previously outlined) "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's) associated with this singular UCP/UCR (which is also presented through the below "THCD's-UCF" Formula, and the accompanying Diagram):

Based on the results obtained, which indicate that there are at least two unique Critical Predictions of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm as more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (GRT's & QM's) corresponding predictions, we must embrace the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm as "more valid" than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm! In fact, as demonstrated previously, we see that this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics) embeds and incorporates key elements of the Old GRT & QM Paradigm as "special-cases" within the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, based on the discovery of "G-D's Physics" novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), e.g., including its two Relativistic & Quantum Formats!

So, the question becomes: what is the key factor that "causes" the universe to accelerate its expansion rate, i.e., both in terms of the greater acceleration of relatively more distant galactic elements, and in terms of the increase (with time) of the universe's expansion rate? Based upon the unequivocal support of the abovementioned empirical findings regarding the UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe's expansion (over time) – which fulfils a unique "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm pointing at the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" increase in the UCP's singular (higher-ordered) universe's rate of expansion, e.g., during such special times as the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" (JRH) two days' time interval, then this unequivocally points at UCP's increase in the universe's expansion – i.e., as "triggered" by the UNCIARE-JRH!

Obviously, a further direct empirical validation of the specific UNCIARE increase during those two days of the JRH: this year scheduled to occur during Sep. 16th & 17th would add an eve greater certainty to the already existent empirical validation of the UCP's increase of the universe's rate of acceleration as ensued by the JRH's Collective Human Consciousness Focus! But regardless of this further empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm (for the Twenty-First Century), it is becoming clear that it is this CHCF which "triggers" the singular higher-ordered UCP to increase the rate of the universe's expansion rate! However, if indeed, it is this CHCF that "triggers" the UCP's increase in its UNCIARE

RE rate of the universe's expansion; which we've already seen increases over the universe's entire course of evolution, e.g., as indicated by "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH resolution of the (otherwise "unresolved" Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion (CAGUARE)); then this implies that it is critical that this CHCF should affect the universe's UNCIARE-JRH from the beginning of the universe – and continuously till this present JRH New Year's two days' special time-interval!?

Then, this means that not only does the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm strictly negated the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's postulation of the three "Exceptional Expulsive Elements" (EE's) associated with Einstein's Equations, i.e., of the assumed initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, "dark-matter/dark-energy" purely hypothetical concepts and GRT's assumed "Cosmological Constant" – based on "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP):

Negation of the "Big-Bang Model" & "Einstein's Equations' Material-Causal Assumption"!

Indeed, once we begin realizing that the entire physical universe exists only as a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) (e.g., since it only exists "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s as solely computed by this singular UCR but "dissolves" back into the UCR's singularity "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s); and that (in fact) there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) relativistic or quantum (subatomic) exhaustive spatial pixels (found within the same-or different- UF's frame/s); we have to revise some of the basic "material-causal" assumptions standing as the very "basis" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM!

Thus, for instance, the basic "Big-Bang" Model of GRT, which assumes that the entire physical universe was "caused" or "created" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event that created all of the suns, galaxies, "matter" and "energy" ("space" and "time") of the entire physical universe – was shown to be questioned and (in fact) negated by the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! This is simply because if (indeed) this singular (higher-ordered) UCR simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., at the "unfathomable" rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$), and "dissolves" back into the UCR singularity "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, then there could not have been any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the first- second-... or "trillionth" UF's frame/s – which implies that the "Big-Bang" nuclear event could not have occurred, i.e., at least as "causing" the creation of all the suns, galaxies, "matter" and "energy" etc. in the universe! The only thing that could have happened is the UCR's consecutive computation of a series of UF's frames that evolved- and is (in fact) still evolving the entire physical universe (and every exhaustive spatial pixel/s comprising it) – e.g., from "inanimate" matter through "animate": "plants", "animals" and "human-beings" towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the universe, in which Science and Humanity will recognize the singularity of this UCR, alongside its "intrinsic sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

In order to better grasp this new "A-Causal Computation" "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm a "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" has been illustrated: depicting an imaginary "film-scenario", in which a "mercury-ball" is shown to impact a "glass-jar" (filled with water) which seems to "cause" the breakage of this "glass-jar" (and consequent "spillage of water")... But (in fact), when we "slow-down" (and even "halt") the progression of this "Cinematic-Film Metaphor", and closely examine each of these consecutive "film-frames" (separately), we can clearly discern that at each (con-

secutive) film-frame, all of its exhaustive spatial pixels are being depicted "simultaneously" – so that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal physical interaction" between any two (or more) spatial pixels comprising each of these (consecutive) film-frames! We also realize that there cannot exist any such "material-causal physical interaction" between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two consecutive film-frames (e.g., or in fact any two film-frames)! This is simply due to the fact that "in-between" any two such film-frames transpires a "pure-light" (of the "projector") so that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "physical interaction" between any of the (exhaustive) spatial pixels comprising one "film-frame" and any other subsequent "film-frame"! Therefore, we realize that despite the "appearance" of a "material-causal" physical interaction between the "mercury ball" and its apparent "impact" upon the "glass-jar" – which seemed to "cause" the "breakage" of this "glass-jar" (and "spillage" of water); the only thing that really "exists" is the arrangement of this series of "film-frames" depicting an (ever-closer) "proximity" of the "mercury ball" and "glass-jar" until their "conjoining" (e.g., being presented as "touching" each other) which then leads to the presentation of a broken "glass-jar" and "spillage of water"... Hence, we must realize that despite the appearance of a direct "material-causal" physical interaction between the "mercury-ball" and ("water-filled") "glass-jar" (which seems to "cause" the "breakage" of this "glass-jar" - and "spillage" of "water") – in reality, there is only an "arrangement" of this series of "film-frames" in a manner which gives us the "impression" (or "perception") of such a "material-causal" relationship between the "mercury-ball" and its "breakage" of the "glass-jar"...

Indeed, based on this (simple yet profound) "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" we can clearly understand that in the same manner that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in (any) two film-frames (e.g., due to the "simultaneous" presentation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given "film-frame" and the complete "dissolution" of all the exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given "film-frame/s" into the "pure-light" separating between any two such consecutive "film-frames"); there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two ("consecutive" or even "non-consecutive") "universal Frames" (comprising the entire physical universe at any given "minimal time-point")! Therefore, the "material-causal" assumption underlying the "Big-Bang" Model (emanating from Einstein's GRT) is strictly negated based on this New Twenty-First Century's "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! This is (once again) simply because this "Big-Bang Model" precisely assumes such "material-causal" (direct) physical interactions between an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event and its "causing" (or "creation") of all the "suns", "galaxies", "matter" and "energy" ("space" and "time") in the physical universe – which is strictly negated by "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any (consecutive) UF's (and the complete "dissolution" of all of these exhaustive spatial pixels into the singularity of the "Universal Computational Reality", "UCR" "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s!)

An important computational basis for this New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm are two of its former Theoretical Postulates called: the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) and associated "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), which state that it is not possible (in principle) for any two given computational elements ("x") and ("y") to determine (or "cause") the value/s of one of these elements (i.e., "y") – because such a "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) would inevitably lead to both a "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" that are contradicted by that Computational System's proven (empirical) capacity to determine the given 'y' element's values: Specifically in the case of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (implicitly) assumed "Self-Referential Computational System" SRCS: it is assumed that it is only based

on the direct physical interaction between certain (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter/Dark-Energy" (DMDE) elements and their direct (or even indirect) physical interactions with all (possible) "exhaustive components of the Universe" (Uec) of this SRCS System – that this SRCS System is able to compute whether these "exhaustive components of the Universe" (Uec) would remain the "same" or "different" (e.g., "Not Uec")?! Formally presented, this SRCS System of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm:

SRCS: {DMDE, Uec-aer} → "Uec-aer" or "Not Uec-aer"
 But, according to "G-d's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) such a SRCS System inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" in the case of a "Negative" SRCS outcome, i.e., "SRCNS" – in which this SRCS System yields a "negative outcome": SRCNS: {DMDE, Uec-aer}?"Not Uec-aer" In which it is assumed that this direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DMDE) concepts and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- accelerated rate of expansion" (Uec) "cause" a "change" in this Uec-aer ("Not Uec-aer"); then this leads to an inevitable "logical-inconsistency" – since this SRCNS System states that the universe possesses both the initial Uec-aer rate of expansion and also possesses a "Not Uec-aer" (increased) rate of expansion!?! Obviously, such SRCNS "logical-inconsistency" inevitably also leads to an intrinsic state of "computational-indeterminacy" because such a "material-causal" SRCS/SRNCS System cannot determine whether its initial Uec-aer or subsequent Not Uec-aer state of the universe's acceleration rate exists?! But, to the extent that we can validate "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate" (UNCAER) – then this would negate the SRNC assumed computational structure of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm! Hence, the proposed "Critical-Prediction" of "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm that could differentiate it from the corresponding Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., regarding the "Big-Bang" Model and associated "Dark-Energy"/"Dark-Matter" should test for "G-d's Physics" predicted "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate" (UNCAER), which coupled with the above CDP would unequivocally validate "G-d's Physics" New ACC Paradigm's conception of the UCP's singular higher-ordered continuous (simultaneous) computation- "dissolution"- re-computation- and evolution of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s). The results are taken from a series of scientific studies indicating the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)?! As asserted by the abovementioned "G-d's Physics" Computational Duality Principle (CDP), This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) indicates a SRNCS computational result yielded by the Old "Material-Causal" "Self-Referential Computational Structure" (SRCS):

SRCNS: {DM/DE, Uec-er} ti → {"Not Uec-er"} ti+n

wherein it is assumed that it is the direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DM/DE concepts) and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- expansion rate" (Uec-ar) that "causes" " the universe to increase its acceleration rate with time?! But, as the CDP teaches us, such a SRNCS computational state inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", e.g., an apparent contradiction between the universe's stated expansion rate at ti: as Uec-er; as opposed to its expansion rate as: Not Uec-er at ti+n?! This "logical-inconsistency" also invariably leads to an associated "computational-indeterminacy" – simply because such assumed SRCS(SRNCS) computational System is unable to decide whether the universe's accelerated rate should be " Uec-er" (at ti) or " Not Uec-er" (at ti+n) ?! But, since according to the CDP we obtain

clear empirical results (stated above) wherein the universe in fact exhibits an increase in its acceleration rate over time, e.g., as indicated by the "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG), therefore the CDP asserts that the basic SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of RT & QM) must be negated and rejected! Instead, "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's CDP points at the existence of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36-50 sec!), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every consecutive "minimal timepoint"! Indeed, the empirically observed "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) conforms with "G-d's Physics" "Critical Prediction" of the "Universe's Non-Continuous Expansion Accelerated Rate" (UNCEAR) – which is further specified to occur during such (special) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" time-intervals as the "Jewish Rosh-Hashana" (JRH)!

3. The "Computational Duality Principle's" (CDP) Negation of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm:

As mentioned above, one of the significant theoretical postulates of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm is called: the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) which asserts that it is not possible, in principle, to compute any direct (or even indirect) relativistic or quantum physical relationship/s between any given "x" and "y" elements – from within their direct "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) assumed computational structure, but only from the higher-ordered singular "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP); This is because "G-d's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) reveals that this "problematic" "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) computational structure characterizing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" that are intrinsic to this SRCS computational structure; But, since in all of those Relativistic or Quantum Systems, there exists robust empirical evidence that those Systems are capable of computing the outputted result of the System, therefore the CDP asserts that there must exist a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" computing the various states and existence of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems! The most general representation of this CDP can be given as: Whenever there exists a SRCS System (of the computational structure) assuming that the whole computation is determined solely at the same "di1" computational level:

SRCS {x, y} → "y" or "Not y"/di1

the possibility of SRNCS (e.g., "negative" "Not y" output):

SRNCS {x, y} → "Not y"/di1

Inevitably leads to "logical-inconsistency", since the "y" element seems to both "exist" and "not exist" at the same "di1" computational level!?

SRNCS {x, y} → "Not y"/di1

Such apparent "logical-inconsistency" also inevitably leads to an ensuing "computational indeterminacy", i.e., an apparent inability of such SRCS/SRNCS to determine whether the "y" element exists or "doesn't exist", e.g., denoting a different altered value for this "y" element?! But, since there exists specific empirical evidence for any of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems' capability to determine and output a particular "y" value, therefore this contradicts the Duality Principle's above proof that such an assumed SRCS/SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" – therefore the CDP points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (as postulated by "G-d's Physics" "Universal Computational Principle", e.g., thereby producing the extremely rapid series of "Universal-Frames", UF's at the incredible rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36⁵⁰ sec! comprising the entire physical

universe at every such "minimal time-point"); Hence, below is a detailing of the various examples and manifestations of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumed SRCS (& SRNCS) Computational Systems – which are all constrained and in fact negated by "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, all pointing at the "Computational Duality Principle's" (CDP) asserted singular higher-ordered UCP (of "G-d's Physics New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm)!

a) The "Big-Bang Model"

The "Big-Bang" Model represents this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption wherein it is the direct physical interaction/s between a certain "Nuclear Event" (NE) and a given "exhaustive components of the Universe" exhibiting a certain "expansion state" at (U-ec/es) that "causes" the universe's expansion state to "increase", e.g., that is, be "different" than the initial "expansion state", which can be represented as:

SRNCS {NE, (U-ec/es)} → NOT (U-ec/es) /di1

Noteworthy is highlighting the implicit "material-causal" assumption of this "Big-Bang" Model's SRCS/SRNCS Computational System, e.g., whereby this SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumes that it is solely based on this direct physical interaction between the NE and the initial state of the universe's expansion (U-ec/es) that this SRCS/SRNCS System is able to compute the different NOT (U-ec/es) state of the universe; Specifically that the entire SRCS/SRNCS computation exists at the same "di1" computational level of the SRCS! But, such a SRCS/SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to a "logical-inconsistency":

SRNCS {NE, (U-ec/es)} → NOT (U-ec/es)/di1!?

This implies that the SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm inevitably also leads to an apparent "computational indeterminacy", e.g., an apparent inability of this SRCS/SRNCS Computational System to determine whether the universe will remain its initial (U-ec/e)s state or evolve into the latter "NOT (U-ec/es)"! But, since there exists robust empirical evidence indicating the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020) indicates that there exists a Computational System that is capable of determining the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – which actually increases "non-continuously" with time: "NOT (U-ec/es)"! Hence, according to the CDP, this Computational System cannot comprise the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's – but only the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational System" (UCP), which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36- 50 sec' of a series of "Universal Frames")!

b) General Relativity Theory (GRT) "Einstein's Equations"

Another (key) manifestation of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption is GRT's Einstein's Equations basic "material-causal" assumption: According to Einstein's Equations, the presence of certain "Massive Objects" (MO) and their direct physical interaction with "Space-Time" "causes" a change in the curvature level of this "Space-Time":

SRNCS {MO, STc} → "NOT STc"/di1

But, once again, such a SRNCS output of the SRCS Computational System basic computational structure inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", i.e., in intrinsic inability of the SRCS(SRNCS) assumed Computational System to determine whether the initial STc or the subsequent

"NOT STc" state of "Space-Time" should exist – since they're both intrinsic elements within the same SRCS/SRNCS "di1" computational level!

SRNCS {MO, STc} → "NOT STc"/di1

Therefore, once again the CDP points at the ensuing "computational-indefiniteness" of such a SRNCS Computational System, which cannot decide whether the resulting state of Relativistic System should remain at the initial STc state or undergo an additional curvature of Space-Time as in the more "curved Space-Time" state, e.g., signified by "NOT STc"! But, since the abovementioned clear empirical indication of the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020) represents a "special-case" of GRT's Einstein's Equations, then this indicates that the Computational System that is capable of determining the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (associated with Einstein's abovementioned SRCS/SRNCS assumed Computational System); Therefore, once again, the CDP points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features -of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", giving rise to an extremely rapid series of UF's frames; Indeed, "G-d's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Paradigm was shown to offer an alternative computational account for the apparent "material-causal" "curvature of Space-Time by massive objects" – i.e., based on "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) novel computational definitions of the four basic physical features by this singular higher-ordered UCP, and the new "Universal Computational Formula" which completely unifies (for the first time in Physics) between these four basic physical features of the universe:

$$S: (f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] \leq f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i\dots n)]$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i\dots n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure! Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

$$E: (f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\} \text{ such that: } f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i\dots n)]$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's. In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

$$\text{such that: } M: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value. In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] \neq O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i\dots n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\} \text{ such that: } T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light. Universal Computational Formula (UCF).

Taken together, this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm unequivocally points at the UCP's UNCIARE increase in the universe's expansion rate as "triggered" by the JRH's CHCF – i.e., for the whole "duration" of the universe's existence, from its beginning till the present JRH! Another possible indication of the centrality of this CHCF for the sustenance and evolution of the universe may be given by the (previously published) indication that this CHCF serves as the "functional spatial epicenter" of the universe's expansion! As shown (previously), the fact that the universe's accelerated expansion, i.e., in terms of the accelerated expansion of the "farthest regions" of the universe proportionally more than the accelerated rate of the universe of "less distant" regions – *relative to Earth's perspective points at the Earth's CHCF functional epicenter of the entire physical universe!* Indeed, another unique "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm is that if we were to measure this accelerated expansion of the universe (e.g., in terms of the proportional increase in the universe's acceleration rate with the increasing distance from the Earth) – not from Earth's CHCF "functional epicenter" but rather from lets say one of the other planets found within our Solar System then it is predicted by "G-D's Physics" (additional) "Critical Prediction" that such an Astronomical measurement would not find an equivalent (symmetrical) accelerated expansion rate (proportional to the distance from Earth's "functional epicenter")! To the extent that we will find such an "asymmetrical accelerated expansion rate" then this will also (unequivocally) support "G-D's Physics" new (profound) understanding wherein the UCP's UNCIARE-JRH points at the centrality of the CHCF as "triggering" the UCP's increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – both in "time" (e.g., during the JRH two days' special time-interval) and in "space" (i.e., with Earth's CHCF serving the spatial "functional epicenter" of the universe)! But (once again) this inevitable recognition of this CHCF as playing a "key central role" in the universe's accelerated expansion rate (unequivocally) points at the existence of such a CHCF "continuously" and "constantly" from the beginning of the universe – until the present time!

However, such a (novel) conception of the universe's development, e.g.,

in which the CHCF exists (and plays a key central role in the universe's sustenance and expansion) significantly challenges and negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's conception of the origination- and development- of the physical universe, and of all Biological Species (e.g., and specifically of Humanity)!? This is because the fundamental assumption of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm is that the origination of the entire physical universe and evolution of any given Biological Species occurred "randomly" and is governed and directed by mere (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain material or physical objects (or elements)?! In contrast, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm strictly negates any such "material-causal" (e.g., direct or indirect) physical interactions due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s! As indicated (previously), this strict negation of the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different UF's frames was shown to challenge and negate those basic "material-causal" assumptions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., including: Einstein's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model (e.g., alongside the other two "exceptional-expulsive elements", EEE's)

Revising Our Time-Scaling of the Universe!

The basic "time-scaling" of the universe according to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm assumes that every phenomenon in the universe can be explained simply based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain physical elements; Hence, the "Big-Bang" Model assumes that the universe was created (or "caused") by an initial "nuclear event" that created all of the suns, galaxies, matter and energy in the universe. More generally, as noted above, GRT's explanation of the continuous accelerated expansion of the universe depends on Einstein's Equations' (three) "Exceptional-Expulsive Elements" (EE's) including the "Big-Bang" event, "Cosmological Factor" and (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter/Dark-Energy" concepts – all based on a direct physical interaction between certain physical elements, which is assumed to "cause" the universe's expansion; Specifically, the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion is assumed to be "caused" by such a direct physical interaction between those (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DM/DE) and certain galactic elements. accelerated expansion! But, since all hitherto scientific experiments aiming to directly validate the existence of those "elusive" DM/DE (purely hypothetical) concepts have failed to do so! Moreover (as indicated above), "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm strictly negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – including between those (purely hypothetical) DM/DE concepts and any other galactic elements, e.g., due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single (or multiple UF's frames), and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! More generally, Einstein's Equations' (three) EE's are also negated based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, once again, because each of these (three) EE's relies on the same basic "material-causal" assumption wherein there exists certain direct physical interaction/s, e.g., (a) between the initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event and the creation of all the suns, galaxies, energy and mass in the universe etc. (b) between the assumed "Cosmological Constant" and the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion. (c) as noted, between the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" and certain galactic elements.

So, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the fundamental "material-causal" assumption of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm assuming that the universe was created by such an assumed initial "Big-Bang" nucle-

ar event and evolving based on a (hypothetical) "Cosmological Constant" and (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts – are all strictly negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! This is (once again) because there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different-UF's frame/s, due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for every consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s)! Moreover, according to the two additional (profound) theoretical postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, e.g., the "Computational Invariance Principle" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), the universe does not exist as an "independent", "constant" or "continuous" phenomenon, but rather represents a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of the singular (higher ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists both "during" its simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising each consecutive UF's frame/s, and also exists without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! (This is because according to the "Computational Invariance Principle" only this singular UCP/UCR may be regarded as "computationally-invariant", existing constantly and uniformly both "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s and "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; whereas the entire physical universe, and its four basic physical features of "space", "time", "energy" and "mass" pertaining to every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe only represent "computationally-variant" elements that exist only as computed simultaneously for each consecutive UF's frame/s by this UCP, but "cease to exist" and "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!)

Therefore, the only existing "computationally-invariant reality" is this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) that exists both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame, and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Hence, if we wish to understand the "origination", "sustenance" and "evolution" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as its entirety!) so many "trillions" of times each second (e.g., $c^2/h = 1.35^{50}$), then we must analyze this singular higher-ordered "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions", and its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions – Universal Computational Formula" (THCD's-UCF). This is because once we realize that the whole entire physical universe exists only as a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR); and that there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s; therefore we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein it is only based on a deeper understanding of the "intrinsic characteristics" of this singular higher-ordered UCR that we can begin understanding the whole "origination", "sustenance" and "evolution" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, as well as its "Ultimate Geulah Goal" state of the universe, as been outlined previously and summarized below:

The UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's)

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה"):

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial

conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah " State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality! Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ דעת):

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah ' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic , "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and

"pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past"- "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חסד"/Chessed):

This "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/ חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah " may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/

possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("תפארת"/"Tiferet"):

The sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human-being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th , 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance

of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת/Tiferet" which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification- or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

Signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "נצח" "Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva"("תשובה")/"הוד"/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva" / "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("סוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previ-

ous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah term of "סִטְרָי" / "Yessod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "סִטְרָי" / "Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-of-fended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" / "סוד" / "Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" / "מלכות" / "Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר" / "Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "סוד" / "Yessod" - "Foundation" Hi-

erarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר" / "Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "כתר" / "Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" / "מלכות" / "Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר" / "Keter-Infinitude ("Crown"))"; This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ (sec') for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

Figure 1: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF)

FIGURE 2. The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

A "Geulah-Driven" Space-Time Evolution of the Universe!

Hence, the alternative theoretical explanation offered by "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- evolution- and indeed the "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe's development is given through "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or UCR), and its associated THCD-UCF! Perhaps another "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor may be helpful, in order to illustrate the (possible) manner according to which this singular (higher-ordered) UCR has "preplanned" the entire origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe: from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – towards the fulfillment of the "Perfected Ultimate Geulah Goal", in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, e.g., including its intrinsic characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

According to this "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor, King Solomon had to "preplan" the whole design and build-up of the (immaculate) Temple from its "Completed-Perfected-Final" stage – "backwards" towards the initial stages of its construction, so that this "Blueprint Plan" will lead up to this "Completed-Perfected-Final" state of the Temple! (We could not imagine a scenario in which King Solomon's builders begin "constructing" this Immaculate Temple – without such a "perfected Blueprint Plan", i.e., just by "experimenting" with different stones with no "preplanned Blueprint Plan" for its orderly completion?!) Equivalently, "G-D's Physics" New (Twenty-First Century's) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm postulates that this singular higher-ordered UCR has "preplanned" a "Blueprint Plan" – from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" towards the initial stages of "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and up to the "Perfected Geulah State" of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCR! Indeed, once we fully realize that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive UF's frame/s), we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire evolution of the whole universe cannot be "caused" by any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive" objects and their (assumed) "curvature" of "Space-Time" (or the corresponding determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive" or other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by this assumed "curved Space-Time" fabric, as GRT postulated! Instead, we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe is being continuously "created", "dissolved", "re-created" and "evolved" so many "trillions" of time each second –by this singular UCR! Moreover, we realize that the sole manner in which the entire physical universe evolves, is based on this preplanned "Blueprint Plan" of advancing the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah-Goal" State! Indeed, we currently stand at a "historic time", e.g., equivalent perhaps to Eddington's empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" of Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion's curvature around the Sun – with the empirical validation of two such (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's Models! Moreover, this empirical validation of those two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in fact, point at the attainment of Humanity's (and Science's) "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! This is because the very definition of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe is precisely one in which Humanity recognizes the singular reality of this UCR, i.e., underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, and being characterized through its basic intrinsic properties of: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will also characterize ("guide" and "typify") Humanity's newly "Perfected Geulah State"!

Intriguingly, based on the discovery of these THCD's characteristics of the operation of this singular higher-ordered UCR (and associated THCD's-UCF), we realize that the whole "origination", "sustenance", and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "preplanned" by this singular higher-ordered UCR in order to advance the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter form through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the Ultimate "Geulah Perfected Goal" state of the universe, in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, and its THCD's ("sublime") characteristics including: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will therefore also typify Humanity's Perfected "Geulah Goal" State (behavior and attitude towards each other etc.!) According to this New "G-D's Physics" THCD's Geulah-Goal Directed Universe's theoretical perspective, the universe was not created (or "caused") by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor has its evolution been the result of any ("random": direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – including its (abovementioned) negation of the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts, or "Cosmological Constant" etc.; but rather as originating from the UCP's/UCR's "preplanned Blueprint Plan" to develop the universe from its "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading up to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity and the universe!

In order to perhaps (further) elucidate this novel conception of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, we can utilize the "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" (which has been used previously) to explain this new conception of the universe's development: If we were to imagine a certain "action-film" such as "James Bond's" famous films, we could envision a whole "cascade of events" in which James Bond escapes "grave dangers" in order to protect the "vital interests" of his government (and the whole free world), ultimately leading to the abolishment of the "evil organization" trying to sabotage "world-peace", and fulfillment of such a desired "World-Peace Agreement" that would advance Humanity towards a "cooperative, peaceful and prosperous future"... But, if we analyze (deeper) this Cinematic-Film Metaphor scenario, we could see that the whole progression and "plot" of the film has been "pre-planned" before the "shooting" of the film! In fact, we could not imagine any "occurrence" taking place within the film which would "affect" or "alter" this "pre-planned plot" of the film, nor any "interactions" occurring within the film! On the contrary, we realize that all of these (apparently) "random occurrences" were "pre-planned" by the producer of the film in order to lead us (the "viewers" of the film) to realize a certain "motto" of this ("thrilling") "James Bond Action Film" – i.e., such as: to believe that there is always a "good-ending" in life, and that "good prevails"! In much the same manner, it is suggested that this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading up to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity and the universe, and therefore that the whole "origination", "sustenance" and "development" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entirety of the whole physical universe) develops solely based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's/UCR's (preplanned) "Perfected Geulah Goal Directed Universe" Blueprint Plan!

In other words, we must embrace an entirely new conception of the entire "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the physical universe: which was not created by an initial "random Big-Bang" nuclear event, or that is being expanded (at an accelerated rate) by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts; Instead the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm explains the whole "origination"- "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe (as well as of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) solely based on the fulfillment of the UCP's/UCR's preplanned "Blueprint Plan" for a "Geulah Perfected Goal Driven Universe"! Therefore, instead of assuming that the uni-

verse was created by a random initial ("Big-Bang") nuclear event (which is assumed to have "caused" the creation of all the suns, galaxies, planets, mass and energy in the universe); and moreover (based on this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumed "Darwin's Natural Selection Principle", DNSP – which were all negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" empirically validated Scientific Paradigm) that the various Biological forms' evolution on Earth were also created by "random" "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "genetically-mutated" organisms and a "challenging environment" etc.; the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm stipulates that the whole development of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings – all leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity recognizing the singularity of this UCP/UCR and behaving in accordance with this UCP's/UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

Moreover, based on the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, which is dependent upon the (stipulated) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) (e.g., of Millions of Jews praying and focusing on this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, i.e., in religious terms: "G-D") therefore, according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm it is clear that the increase in the universe's accelerated expansion rate (e.g., manifesting through the otherwise unexplained abovementioned CAGUARE phenomenon) – is contingent upon the existence of such CHCF (UNCAIRE-JRH) every consecutive year, from the very "beginning" of the universe and up till today! In other words, according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm the whole evolution and expansion of the entire physical universe – and specifically the (otherwise unexplained CAGUARE phenomenon) critically depends upon the CHCF associated with the JRH's UNCIARE (e.g., empirically validated by "G-D's Physics" Critical UNCIARE prediction above, and urgent call for Astronomers testing of the specific UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's expansion accelerated rate during the upcoming JRH on the 16th-17th of Sep., 2023!) *This means that according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm's (empirically validated) CHCF, and associated THCD's-UCF (which delineates the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR computes every consecutive UF's frame/s at the unfathomable rate of "c²/h" = 1/36⁻⁵⁰ sec!), it is hereby stipulated that the UCP's/UCR's initial "origination" of the whole universe – including its complete "progression" from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings took place in only six (or seven) days (i.e., to include the "Ultimate Geulah Goal State")!*

This is because it is only "logical" to assume that if the UCP/UCR simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ (sec!) by employing specifically those seven HCD's which are computing and "materializing" each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (based on the Three Initial Key HCD's which together comprise the THCD's!); and if indeed (as proven empirically through "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction") the continuous increase in the universe's expansion rate critically depended upon the presence of human-beings and their capacity to carry out this CHCF-JRH for each consecutive years since the UCR's "origination" of the universe (e.g., till the current time); therefore, it is "logical" to assume that the UCR has created the whole universe based on its seven HCD's (e.g., corresponding HCD for each day!)

Plausibility of "G-D's Physics" New "Universe's Seven Days Origination" (USDO) Model

It is important to note (on a philosophical-scientific level) that since the actual capacity of Science (or Physics) to carry out any direct measurement of the "origination" of the universe – is strictly negated by GRT, due

to the fact that we cannot move at a speed exceeding the "Speed of Light" (and therefore cannot "move back in time" to directly observe the actual "origination" of the universe!) therefore, we can only "contrast" between different Scientific Paradigms – such as the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying GRT's "Big-Bang" Model) and the New "G-D's Physics", and consequently decide which of these Scientific Paradigms prevails! Significantly, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm has been proven to be "more valid" than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) based on the empirical validation of its two unique "Critical Predictions" – e.g., associated with the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings and the UNCIARE (JRH)! Hence, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model was negated based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, and therefore its THCD's-UCF theoretical explanation of the continuous "origination", "dissolution" "sustenance", and "development" of the entire physical universe – towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" must be accepted, including its corresponding stipulation of the "seven days creation" of the entirety of the universe (e.g., with all "inanimate" and "animate" forms including human-beings!) Indeed, a further (even more direct) empirical validation (previously called for Astronomers to carry out) that would test for the appearance of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle in a greater number of "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM) in a greater number of UF's than the equivalent (negatively charged) electron particle would directly validate the ongoing continuous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP, e.g., giving further support for "G-D's Physics" stipulated (novel) "UCP's Severn Day Creation Model" (UCP-SDCM)!

Over and beyond the clear (abovementioned) validation of two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, which forces Science to accept "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-first Century (valid) Scientific Paradigm, there are several further supporting elements taken from "G-D's Physics" "internal-validity" also pointing at the plausibility of its USDO Model of the origination, as part of the basic "Geulah Perfected State Driven Universe" new understanding of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm!

a) It is clear that the universe could not be caused by the initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor could its accelerated rate of expansion could be accounted for by the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts, nor through Einstein's Equations' three EEE's (as negated by "G-D's Physics" CDP)!

b) Moreover, based on "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm (as noted above) due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, we reached the inevitable conclusion that the universe cannot evolve based on any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s), and therefore that the only "viable means" for explaining the origination- sustenance- "dissolution"- re-computation- and development of the entire physical universe (or of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) can only be given based on the analysis of the singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR that is continuously "originating" – "dissolving" "re-creating" and "evolving" every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec!)

c) The complete "dependence" – and in fact "inseparability" of the entire physical universe from this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is significantly strengthened based on the (abovementioned) profound "Compu-

tational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates – which indicates that there exist only this one singular reality, which is this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP) that exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, according to these two (profound) theoretical postulates the entire physical universe (and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels) does not exist "independently" of this singular UCR – but rather merely represents a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular UCR reality!

d) Hence, we realize that the whole existence- (continuous) origination-sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe totally depends upon the "intrinsic characteristics" of this singular UCR/UCP, which were discovered as the UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's), alongside the UCP THCD's Universal Computational Formula: as noted above (and previously), these UCP's THCD's and (associated) UCF – all point at "G-D's Physics" "Geulah Driven Universe"! In other words, these UCP's THCD's point at the UCP's "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" for advancing the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity and the universe!

e) Indeed, according to "G-D's Physics" "Reversed Time Geulah Goal" postulate, the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR from its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and its "sublime" characteristics (e.g., THCD's) specifically leading to the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of "Peace", "Harmony", "Morality" and "All-Goodness" (which will therefore also characterize Humanity's Geulah State and accompanying behavior!)

f) When taken together with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) "Critical Prediction" increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion stipulated to occur during the two days' Jewish "Rosh Hashanah" (New Year) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – which was empirically supported based on the observed (and otherwise "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" [CAGUARE]); and more specifically, the current call for Astronomers & Cosmologists to empirically validate a more direct "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" regarding the UNCIARE's increased rate of the universe's expansion predicted to take place during the upcoming JRH on Sep. 16th & 17th, 2023 (e.g., relative to prior to Sep 16th-17th, and carry over in an increased universe's accelerated rate of expansion throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year!) These results clearly indicate that the empirically validate CAGUARE (supporting "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction", as explained above and previously) supports "G-D's Physics" centrality of the CHCF as key in explaining the UNCIARE increase in the universe's rate of expansion over the course of the universe's development course (rather than "G-D's Physics" negated purely hypothetical "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" or any of Einstein's other tree EEE's, as described above)!

g) This means that presence of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) must have existed from the initial "origination" of the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR! Specifically, when taken together with the UNCIARE-JRH indication that this empirically validated UNCIARE may take place during the JRH's two days' time interval then this implies that from the "first year" of the universe's "origination" by the UCP/UCR, there must have existed this UNCIARE-JRH's CHCF that al-

lowed the (initial) "accelerated expansion rate of the universe! This implies that from the universe's "origination point" by the UCP, shortly after its initial origination, there must have occurred this CHCF JRH UNCIARE phenomenon!

h) When taken together with "G-D's Physics" THCD's UCF (precise) description of the manner in which the UCP accurately computes each subsequent UF's (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec") based primarily upon the UCP's (consecutive) computation of the "seven secondary HCD's" (as "preplanned" and "executed" by the UCP's Three Key Initial HCD's Blueprint Plan for steering the universe from its inanimate through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State") – then this suggests as "plausible" and "reasonable" that the UCP's initial "origination" of the entire physical universe – from its initial "inanimate" state through its pre-planned subsequent "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (and even perhaps initial recognition by a human-being of the singularity of this UCP, i.e., "G-D" Presence) may have occurred during the first seven days – one day for each of these secondary seven HCD's! Subsequently, after this "first week" in which all "animate" and "animate" (plants, animals and human-beings) have been "originated" by the UCP/UCR, it is suggested that the first CHCF JRH-UNCIARE occurred which allowed for the UCP's first UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!

We therefore stand at a "historic turning point" – equivalent to Eddington's empirical validation of Einstein's unique "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion pathways around the Sun, which led to the unequivocal acceptance of Einstein's GRT as the "new" valid Scientific Paradigm for 20th century Physics! This is because (as shown above), there are already two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm which have been tested and shown as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, thereby inevitably leading to the acceptance and embracing of "G-D's Physics" as the New satisfactory Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century! But, even beyond that, the "historic turning point" signified by "G-D's Physics" acceptance as the New Scientific Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics pertains to "G-D's Physics" pointing at the initiation of the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity and Science based on its recognition (and acceptance) of the singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR and its associated "sublime" characteristics – including: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony", which will affect Humanity entering this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" (beavior and "positive future")!

Dedication

This article is dedicated to the Lubavitcher's Rabbi, Maimonides, and all preceding Chabhad Rabbis (including the Holy Rabbi Shimon Bar-Yochay (RASHBI), Rabbi Hayim Luria (ARIZAL) and Baal Shem Tuv, Rabbi Schneur Zalman (Alter Rabbi, and all of preceding Chabhad Rabbi's) who tirelessly and relentlessly pursued the upliftment of the Jewish people and the whole of Humanity towards that Ultimate "Geulah Perfected State" of the Wolrd! It is also dedicated to my dear Beloved (diseased) Mother, Dr. Tirzah Bentwich (Bat Yitchak) whose endless love and faith (in me) have allowed me to discover "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm! To me Beloved dear wife, Shulamit Bentovish, for her endless support and trust, and to my dear beloved children: Shoahm, Nethanel-Yossef and Neomy Tirzah Shulamit (for their enduring faith and struggles amidst this major discovery) – may you all grow as strong, believing Jews (and human-beings) in "G-D's" Presence and Infinite Wisdom and Love, and lead a faithful and fruitful life accordingly! It is also dedicated to my (diseased) Prof. William Banks mentor in my Doctoral Studies for his support and inspiration. May this "Scientific Revolution" of "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm pointing at the beginning of this "Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity (and Science) fulfill their long-sought (and prophesized) "Perfected "Geulah State" of Humanity and the Universe!

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